

قرآن اور احادیث میں ایمان والوں کی ذکر کردہ صفات کا ایک جائزہ

ATTRIBUTES OF THE TRUE BELIEVERS IN THE
LIGHT OF QURAN & SUNNAH

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ABSTRACT

Allah has bestowed mankind with various attributes. He has personified those qualities and set an example for the entire nation in the form of his Prophet ﷺ who has the best of the best character so that people can look up to them and follow them. Hence Quran and Sunnah are the keys to attain the excellence in one's character as a guide to inculcate those attributes to become the best and a productive Muslim to not only shine and prosper here but also in the hereafter. So here is a brief analysis of the verses from Quran and Hadith regarding qualities of the true believers.

Keywords: Belief, Fear of Allah, Trust, Taqwa, Impeccability, Fulfill Promise.

کلیدی الفاظ: ایمان، تقویٰ، توکل، عبادات، عفت، وعدہ پورا کرنا۔

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